

A preliminary study on interaction of H₄ histone with DNA in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states[†]

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Abstract : H₄ histone (100 µg/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride showed minimum conductance and absorbance values at 230 nm, 280 nm and A_{λmax} at pH 7.02. So exposition of chromophores was minimum and charge neutralization was maximum at this pH. DNA : H₄ complex (50 : 50 µg/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride was found to be stable in the pH range of 6.68 to 8.86.

Minor variations in binding of H₄ histone with DNA (pH range 6.68 to 7.15) for forming the DNA : H₄ complex (25 : 25 µg/ml) have occurred when 0.9% sodium chloride, 0.15 M and 0.1 M phosphate buffers have been used as solvents. This is evidenced by variation in position of absorption maximum and intensity of absorption maximum. Nature of binding in last two solvents are alike but different for 0.9% sodium chloride. This is due to variations in (i) counter-ion concentration in solution (i.e. PO₄³⁻, HPO₄²⁻, H₂PO₄⁻, Na⁺ and Cl⁻), (ii) exposed functional groups and chromophores (both in far and near UV) of H₄ histone (i.e. imidazole group of histidine, positively charged arginine and lysine) and that of DNA (i.e. -C=C-C=O and -C=C-C=N-) and (iii) charge interactions between amino-acids and peptides of H₄ histone with phosphate groups of DNA. The value of the binding constant for DNA-H₄ complex varied from 3.45 LM⁻¹ (for 0.15 M phosphate buffer) to 3.66 LM⁻¹ (0.1 M phosphate buffer) and to 3.77 LM⁻¹ (for 0.9% sodium chloride). The complex formation of DNA with H₄ histone has also been evidenced by increase in melting temperature by 9 °C more for DNA : H₄ complex than that of DNA.

H₄ histone (25 µg/ml, pH 6.80, 0.15 M phosphate buffer) can be used as *in vitro* biological dosimeter by measuring A_{660nm} with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent in the dose range 30–80 Gy at 1.12 Gy/s. Similarly depletion of H₄ histone from DNA-H₄ complex (25 : 25 µg/ml) as detected by Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (A_{660nm}) can also be used as *in vitro* biological dosimeter in the dose range of 20 to 70 Gy at a dose rate of 1.12 Gy/s. In 0.9% sodium chloride the response for H₄ histone (i.e. A_{280nm}) did not change with dose. But in 0.01 N hydrochloric acid, pH range 3.92–4.44, the response for H₄ histone (i.e. A_{210nm}, A_{220nm} and A_{280nm}) decreased with dose up to 50 Gy for a dose rate of 0.0103 Gy/s. Here it can be used as a dosimeter for intestinal tract. These biological *in vitro* dosimeters may find use in radiation-induced nucleosomal aberration.

Keywords : DNA, H₄ histone, amino acid, lysine.

Introduction

H₄ histone occurs as a dimer in combination with H₃ histone in the nucleosomal core as (H₃-H₄)₂. These two histones are in turn are bound to DNA for forming the nucleosomal core. This stereospecific structural configuration has been resolved at 2.8 Å resolution¹. Some basic structural aspects of H₄ histone like molecular weight

(i.e. 11,282), amino-acid residues per molecule (i.e. 102), lysine : arginine ratio (i.e. 11 : 14) and specific positive charge (i.e. 0.16) have been reported^{2,3}. H₄ histone, obtained from chicken, contains two chains⁴, the length and breadth of first chain are 47 Å and 32 Å and that for second chain are 50 Å and 45 Å respectively. The mean end to end distance is 874 Å and compact volume⁵ is

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11374 (Å)³. The accessibility of these two chains are determining factors for their accommodation inside major groove of nucleosome⁶. The amino-acid carboxy terminal tails of the histones extend from each nucleosome and are subjected to post translational modification including acetylation, phosphorylation⁷ etc. Amino-terminal tail regions of H₄ histone contains 4 lysine residues located⁸ at positions 5, 8, 12 and 16.

Recently we have reported the radiation-induced alterations of H₃ histone and H₃-DNA complex⁹. It has been found that H₃-histone is radio-resistant. But H₁ histone¹⁰ and H₁-DNA complex¹¹ are radio-sensitive. As H₄ histone is present in the core of nucleosome both H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ complex may be radio-resistant. Moreover, as H₄ histone contains two chains, both H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ complex may be influenced by solvent composition in which both the biopolymers are dissolved, thereby causing configurational alteration.

So the main aim of the present study are two-fold : (i) to bring out configurational alterations in H₄ histone and H₄-DNA complex in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states, especially in the physiological range of pH and (ii) to find out the potentiality of H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ complex as *in vitro* biological dosimeters in physiological pH range.

Materials and methods :

Calf Thymus DNA (Cat No. D1501, Lot No. H9526) and H₄ histone (Cat No. H6005, Lot No. 39F, 8080) were obtained from Sigma Chemical Company, USA. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was obtained from Centre for Biotechnology, CSIR. All other compounds (e.g. sodium chloride, hydrochloric acid, di-sodium hydrogen phosphate, sodium di-hydrogen phosphate, sodium hydroxide etc.) were obtained from E. Merck and Company. Tripled distilled water was used.

Stock solutions of DNA and H₄ histone were prepared in 0.9% sodium chloride (pH 6.50–7.10), 0.15 M and 0.1 M phosphate buffers (pH 6.80–7.00). H₄ histone was added to DNA in solution in these solvents in a dropwise manner slowly with stirring as reported¹². UV absorption measurements for all the biopolymers and their complexes under different experimental conditions were taken in GBC UV-visible spectrophotometer, Australia (wavelength accuracy ± 0.5 nm and absorbance accuracy ± 0.001) at different equilibrated pH values (Toshniwal pH meter, Chandigarh, pH accuracy ± 0.01). The conductance values of H₄ histone solutions were measured in

a conductivity bridge (Elico, Hyderabad of accuracy ± 1 μ Mho). Melting profile studies of DNA : H₄ complex (25 : 25 μ g/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride was carried out by heating the complex at a rate of 0.1 °C/min by keeping this solution in a thermostatically controlled cuvette (temperature accuracy ± 0.1 °C, dwell time 1 min) and measuring A_{260nm} values of the complex at different temperatures.

Irradiation of solutions of H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ histone complex were done in Gamma cell 220 of Atomic Energy of Canada for a low dose rate and Gamma chamber 5000 of Board of Radiation and Isotopes, Mumbai for high dose rate. Equal volumes of solutions of biopolymer at 10 °C were taken in pyrex tubes of 1 cm uniform diameter and 1 mm wall thickness. Both the irradiation facilities had circular geometries. Determination of dose rates were done by FBX dosimeter (low dose rate¹³) and Fricke dosimeter (for high dose rate¹⁴). The absorbed dose measurements were correct up to $\pm 3\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ in Gamma cell 220 and Gamma chamber 5000 respectively¹⁵.

Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added to the irradiated solutions of either H₄ histone or DNA : H₄ complex was prepared in 0.9% sodium chloride solution. To these solutions 0.15 M phosphate buffer was added for bringing down the pH to 6.80 from 7.00. Variation in A_{660nm} values for different H₄ histone concentrations were noted for calibration purposes. For gamma irradiated H₄ histone at a fixed concentration (50 μ g/ml), the different H₄ histone concentrations at different absorbed doses were calculated from A_{660nm} values. H₄ histone depleted from DNA : H₄ complex (25 : 25 μ g/ml) by gamma irradiation and this was complexed with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. The amount of its depletion (μ g/ml) was calculated with the help of calibration curve and measurement of A_{660nm} values.

Results

UV spectral characteristics of DNA, H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ complex in the unirradiated state :

The calibration curves for DNA, H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ in equal concentration ratio in 0.9% sodium chloride were found to be linear up to 50 μ g/ml, 100 μ g/ml and 50 : 50 μ g/ml for DNA, H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ complex respectively (Fig. 1).

It will be observed from Table 1 that in 0.9% sodium chloride, H₄ histone (100 μ g/ml) did not show any substantial variation in A_{280nm} values throughout the experi-

Fig. 1. Calibration curves of DNA, H₄ histone and DNA-H₄ complex in 0.9% sodium chloride : (O) DNA, pH range 6.10-6.50, A_{258-260nm}, (●) DNA : H₄ in equal concentration ratio, pH range 6.15-6.46, A_{258-260nm}, (■) H₄ histone, pH range 5.50-6.50, A_{204nm}, (▲) H₄ histone, pH range 5.50-6.50, A_{280nm}.

mental pH range except at pH 9.07. Depending upon pH, position of absorption maximum varied from 224 nm to 256 nm. In either acidic pH values of 2.85, 3.52, 3.92 and 4.52 or alkaline pH values of 8.72 and 9.07 the absorption values were relatively sharp whereas at neutral pH values of 6.50 and 7.02 the absorption peaks were relatively broad. At pH 7.02, A_{λmax}, A_{280nm} and conductance values were found to be minimum (Table 1).

The UV absorption spectral parameters of DNA : H₄ complex (50 : 50 µg/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride in the pH range from 1.57 to 8.86 revealed that there is a blue shift in λ_{max} from 272 nm to 256 nm. The λ_{min} value has occurred at 230 nm in the pH range 3.02 to 8.86 and the absorbance intensities have decreased. The A_{λmax} values have increased with increase of pH, though after neutral pH of 6.68 it has decreased at pH 8.86 (Table 2).

Table 1. Variation in the UV spectral parameters of H₄ histone as a function of pH

Concentration - 100 µg/ml; Solvent - 0.9% sodium chloride				
pH	λ _{max} (nm)	A _{λmax}	A _{280nm}	Conductance at 50 Hz (µ Mho)
2.85	228-230	0.24 ± 0.022	0.18 ± 0.001	630 ± 10
3.52	224-230	0.22 ± 0.004	0.17 ± 0.002	530 ± 10
3.92	230-232	0.20 ± 0.005	0.16 ± 0.003	470 ± 05
4.52	228-232	0.22 ± 0.002	0.17 ± 0.004	410 ± 05
6.50	226-238	0.25 ± 0.003	0.16 ± 0.005	190 ± 10
7.02	246-256	0.18 ± 0.002	0.16 ± 0.005	140 ± 10
8.72	232-238	0.19 ± 0.001	0.18 ± 0.003	170 ± 15
9.07	234-240	0.25 ± 0.003	0.25 ± 0.004	230 ± 05

N=3

Table 2. UV absorption spectral parameters of DNA-H₄ complex as a function of pH

DNA : H ₄ - 50 : 50 µg/ml; Solvent - 0.9% sodium chloride				
pH	λ _{max} (nm)	A _{λmax}	λ _{min} (nm)	A _{λmin}
1.57	272	0.76 ± 0.005	-	-
1.94	272	0.85 ± 0.010	-	-
2.68	268	0.88 ± 0.007	-	-
3.02	260	0.88 ± 0.006	230	0.70 ± 0.005
6.68	256	1.93 ± 0.006	230	0.60 ± 0.007
8.86	256	1.14 ± 0.005	230	0.62 ± 0.006

N=3

In Table 3 the UV spectral characteristics of DNA (25 µg/ml), H₄ (25 µg/ml) and DNA : H₄ complex (25 : 25

Table 3. UV spectral characteristics of DNA-H₄ complex in different solvents

Properties	Solvent - 0.9% sodium chloride	Solvent - 0.15 M phosphate buffer	Solvent - 0.1 M phosphate buffer
Concentration (µg/ml)	DNA - 25 H ₄ - 25	DNA - 25 H ₄ - 25	DNA - 25 H ₄ - 25
pH	DNA : H ₄ - 25 : 25 DNA - 6.79 H ₄ - 7.02	DNA : H ₄ - 25 : 25 DNA - 7.00 H ₄ - 7.00	DNA : H ₄ - 25 : 25 DNA - 6.78 H ₄ - 7.15
λ _{max} (nm)	DNA : H ₄ - 6.90 DNA - 204, 258-260 H ₄ - 204 DNA : H ₄ - 258-260	DNA : H ₄ - 7.00 DNA - 210, 256-260 H ₄ - 208 DNA : H ₄ - 212, 252-258	DNA : H ₄ - 7.00 DNA - 210-212, 260 H ₄ - 208-210, 220 (hump) DNA : H ₄ - 215, 245-260
A _{λmax} near UV	H ₄ - DNA - 1.44 DNA : H ₄ - 0.80	DNA - 0.43 H ₄ - DNA : H ₄ - 0.68	DNA - 0.54 H ₄ - DNA : H ₄ - 0.72
A _{λmax} far UV	H ₄ - 0.50 DNA - 0.80 DNA : H ₄ - 1.44	H ₄ - 1.58 DNA - 1.68 DNA : H ₄ - 1.96	H ₄ - 1.58, 130 DNA - 1.72 DNA : H ₄ - 1.96
N = 3			

µg/ml) in three different solvents at neutral pH range (pH 6.78 to 7.15) have been demonstrated. In all these three solvents the equilibrated pH of DNA : H₄ complex is in between the pH of DNA and H₄ histone.

In 0.9% sodium chloride H₄ histone showed an absorption maximum at 204 nm and a regular decrease in absorption intensity from 220 nm up to 300 nm. In this solvent DNA showed two absorption maxima, one at 204 nm and another at 258-260 nm. The DNA : H₄ complex showed one absorption maximum at 258-262 nm. The absorption intensity at far UV (i.e. 204 nm) and near UV (i.e. 258-262 nm) is less for DNA : H₄ complex compared to DNA.

In 0.15 M phosphate buffer, H₄ histone, DNA and DNA : H₄ complex showed distinct absorption maxima at far UV. But in near UV, H₄ histone showed consistent decrease in absorption intensity from 220 to 300 nm. DNA showed two clear absorption maxima, one at 210 nm and another at 260 nm. The DNA : H₄ complex also showed two absorption maxima, one at 212 nm and another at 254-258 nm (broad λ_{max}).

In 0.1 M phosphate buffer, DNA showed absorption maxima at 211-212 nm and 260 nm, H₄ showed an absorption maximum at 210 nm, a hump at 220 nm and thereafter a consistent decrease in absorption intensities with increase in wavelength. DNA : H₄ showed absorp-

tion maxima at 215 nm and a broad absorption maximum from 245 to 260 nm. All these spectral features have been summarized in Table 3.

The melting temperature for the complex of DNA : H₄ (25 : 25 µg/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride at pH 6.80 has been obtained at 80.5 °C from the melting profile curve (Fig. 2).

H₄ histone, prepared in 0.9% sodium chloride, when mixed with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent in 0.15 M phosphate buffer, pH 6.80, showed linearity in absorbance at 660 nm up to 50 µg/ml (Table 4).

Radiation-induced changes in H₄ histone and DNA : H₄ complex :

In 0.01 N hydrochloric acid, pH 3.92-4.44, when H₄ histone (conc. 100 µg/ml) was irradiated at a dose rate of 0.0103 Gy/s, the A_{210nm} and A_{220nm} values decreased linearly with dose, but A_{280nm} values remained unchanged both in 0.01 N hydrochloric acid and 0.9% sodium chloride up to a dose of 50 Gy (Fig. 3).

H₄ histone (50 µg/ml) when complexed with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent in 0.9% sodium chloride solvent with 0.15 M phosphate buffer as neutralizing agent, pH 6.80, showed linear decrease in A_{660nm} values from 30 Gy to 80 Gy at a dose rate of 1.12 Gy/s (Fig. 4).

It has been observed that the amount of depletion of H₄ histone (µg/ml) from DNA : H₄ complex has increased

Fig. 2. Melting profile of DNA : H₄ complex (25 : 25 µg/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride.

Table 4. Calibration for detection of H₄ histone by Folin-Ciocalteu reagent

Solvent - 0.9% sodium chloride; pH 6.80 (maintained by 0.15 M phosphate buffer)

Concentration of H ₄ histone (µg/ml)	A _{660nm}
10	0.036 ± 0.002
20	0.068 ± 0.002
30	0.116 ± 0.004
40	0.144 ± 0.002
50	0.180 ± 0.005

N = 3

linearly with dose up to 70 Gy, beyond which a plateau was obtained (Table 5).

Discussion

UV spectral analysis of biopolymers :

The chromophores of DNA i.e. -C=C-C=N-, responsible for absorption at 258-260 nm¹⁶ and chromophores of H₄ histone namely imidazole group of histidine responsible for absorption at 204 nm¹⁷ and phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan responsible for absorption at 280 nm¹⁸ have increased in proportion with concentration in 0.9% sodium chloride solution. For DNA : H₄ complex the linearity in A_{258-260nm} values with increase in concentration is in between the response for DNA and H₄ histone. As the concentration ratio has in-

creased, increasing number of chromophores of DNA as well as phosphate groups have interacted with ε groups of lysine, guanidine groups of arginine and protonated imidazole groups of histidine from H₄ histone. The resultant exposed chromophores as influenced by counter-ion effect by Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions are responsible for absorption (Fig. 1).

The effect of pH on H₄ histone in terms of variation in position of absorption maximum, its sharpness, at pH 2.85, 3.92 and 4.52; and its broadness at pH 6.50, 7.02, 8.72 and 9.07 are indications of unfolding of the peptide bonds¹⁸ (220 to 240 nm) and modulation of tertiary structure of H₄ histone to different extent. The lysine/arginine ratio being 11 : 14 per molecule, and amino-acid residue being 102 per molecule^{2,3}, the ionization of the amino-acids have occurred to different extent depending on pH. In highly acidic and alkaline media like pH 2.85 and 9.07 maximum ionization of the chromophores (e.g. ε groups of lysine, guanidinium groups of arginine and protonated imidazole groups of histidine) have occurred. But up to pH 8.72 the number of tryptophan, tyrosine and phenylalanine groups¹⁸ (A_{280nm}) have not changed markedly. At pH 7.02 charge neutralization was maximum for all the amino-acids present in H₄ histone, thereby the conductance has become minimum. With increase in pH charge neutralization has increased consistently up to pH 7.02, above which again the conductance has started increasing. The counter-ion effect of large number of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions around negatively and positively charged

Fig. 3. Dose-response relationship of H₄ histone (100 µg/ml) in acidic and neutral medium. Solvent - 0.01 N hydrochloric acid, pH range 3.92-4.44, (●) A_{210nm}, (▲) A_{220nm}, (■) A_{280nm}. Solvent - 0.9% sodium chloride, pH 6.50, (◆) A_{280nm}.

Fig. 4. Dose-response relationship of H₄ histone (concentration 50 µg/ml) in 0.9% sodium chloride, pH 6.80 (maintained by 0.15 M phosphate buffer) complexed by Folin-Ciocalteu reagent at a dose rate of 1.12 Gy/s : (◆) A_{660nm}.

amino-acids at different pH values have also contributed towards chromophoricity and conductance values of H₄ histone (Table 1).

Acid hydrolysis of H₄ histone has resulted in dissociation of this protein from DNA and subsequent decomposition to constituent amino-acids at extremely acidic pH of 1.57, 1.94, 2.68 and 3.02. This has resulted into gradual blue shift of absorption maximum from 272 to 260 nm. But

in neutral pH and slightly alkaline pH of 6.68 and 8.86 absorption maximum has occurred in between 256 and 258 nm. Moreover, at these two pH values λ_{max} , λ_{min} and $A_{\lambda_{min}}$ values are identical. So the chromophoric dispositions are non-variant and the complex is also stable at these two pH values (Table 2).

DNA : H₄ complex (25 : 25 µg/ml) formation have taken place in all the three solvents (e.g. 0.9% sodium

Table 5. Depletion of H₄ histone from DNA-H₄ complex with increasing dose of gamma radiation

DNA : H₄ - 25 : 25 µg/ml; Solvent - 0.9% sodium chloride; pH 6.80; dose rate - 1.12 Gy/s

Dose (Gy)	A _{660nm}	H ₄ -histone (µg/ml)
Unirr.	0.003 ± 0.001	0.00
20	0.010 ± 0.001	3.00
30	0.015 ± 0.002	4.00
40	0.020 ± 0.003	6.00
50	0.030 ± 0.002	8.50
70	0.040 ± 0.003	11.00
90	0.045 ± 0.004	12.50
100	0.045 ± 0.004	12.50

N = 3

chloride, 0.1 M phosphate buffer and 0.15 M phosphate buffer), out of which 0.1 M phosphate buffer has been used by us earlier¹¹, in the pH range 6.78 to 7.15 (Table 3). These are all charge neutralization complexes between negatively charged phosphate groups of DNA and positively charged amino-acids (e.g. ε groups of lysine, guanidinium groups of arginine and protonated imidazole groups of histidine), backbone amides and carbonyl groups of H₄ histone¹⁹. The -C=C-C=N- chromophores of DNA (λ_{max} 258-260 nm), imidazole groups of histidine (at 204 nm) have interacted in complex formation¹⁷. It is a stereospecific binding of H₄ histone in the sites available in DNA. It is mostly n-σ* transition¹⁶ which is responsible for X-peak absorption for complex formation. Nature of binding is alike in 0.1 M and 0.15 M phosphate buffers and distinctly different in 0.9% sodium chloride due to differential counter-ion effect (i.e. PO₄³⁻, HPO₄²⁻, H₂PO₄¹⁻ and Na⁺ and Cl⁻) on the chromophores responsible for binding. Even π-π* transitions¹⁶ (i.e. -C=C-C=O) of DNA have been influenced by phosphate buffers thereby showing λ_{max} at 212 nm with 0.15 M phosphate buffer and 215 nm with 0.1 M phosphate buffer (Table 3).

The melting temperature of DNA : H₄ complex is 9 °C more (80.5 °C for complex and 71.5 °C for DNA) compared to DNA (Fig. 2). The T_m value for this complex has been reported²⁰ to be 87 °C in 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ M EDTA solvent. This is a measure of the thermal energy needed to dislodge all the hydrogen bonds provided by constituent amino-acids of H₄ histone to bind with the -C=C-C=N- and -C=C-C=O chromophores of DNA.

The binding constant of DNA : H₄ complex in the un-

irradiated state can be found in the following manner. The equilibrium of binding of DNA with H₄ histone can be written as

So, the equilibrium binding constant K at 25 °C

$$= \frac{[\text{DNA-H}_4]}{[\text{DNA}] [\text{H}_4]} \quad (2)$$

where [DNA-H₄], [DNA] and [H₄] are the concentrations of the complex, free DNA and free H₄ histone respectively. As the molecular weight of H₄ histone is very small (i.e. 11,282) as compared to DNA (i.e. 6.0 × 10⁶), it can be assumed that all H₄ histone molecules will be completely bound to DNA as there are sufficiently large number of binding sites in DNA. From the UV spectra of DNA, H₄ histone and DNA-H₄ complex (as has been summarized in Table 3), the absorption maximum for the DNA-H₄ complex can be found out. The concentration of DNA-H₄ complex can be found out from calibration curve in Fig. 1. By applying eq. (2) the value of binding constant can be determined. The free DNA and free histone concentrations are 25 µg/ml each. Taking 1.0 × 10⁶ as the molecular weight of nucleohistone (i.e. DNA-H₄ complex) the value of the equilibrium constants have been found to be 3.77 LM⁻¹ in 0.9% sodium chloride, 3.45 LM⁻¹ in 0.15 M phosphate buffer and 3.68 LM⁻¹ in 0.1 M phosphate buffer respectively. The different solvents used for preparation of DNA-H₄ complex will selectively dissolve different amino-acids of H₄ histone and nucleotides of DNA for binding. The hydrophilicity of the amino-acids present in H₄ histone are in the following decreasing order²¹ :

Arg > Asp > His > Glu > Asn > Lys > Gln > Tyr > Ser > Thr > Met > Phe.

Accordingly their probability of binding increases with nucleotides though their association constants are of comparable order of magnitude²².

The Cu-H₄ complex formed by interaction of peptide bonds and amino-acids of H₄ histone with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was responsible for absorption at 660 nm²³. Increase in A_{660nm} values with increase in concentration of H₄ histone clearly demonstrates the formation of increasing amount of Cu-H₄ complex (Table 4).

Analysis of radiation-induced changes in biopolymers :

Unfolding of tertiary structure of H₄ histone and subsequent hydrolysis at pH 3.92 to 4.44 took place initially in 0.01 N hydrochloric acid. Upon irradiation to increas-

ing doses the histidine and peptide bonds have cleaved from H₄ histone thereby A_{210nm} and A_{220nm} values have decreased. But in 0.9% sodium chloride, pH 6.50 to 7.00 the tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine chromophores did not show decrease in A_{280nm} values up to 50 Gy. This may be due to high clustering effect of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions. This helped the chromophores to remain relatively unaffected by increasing dose of gamma radiation (Fig. 3).

The linear decrease in A_{660nm} with increase in dose from 20 to 80 Gy at a dose rate of 1.12 Gy/s is due to destruction of the peptide bonds. Moreover, amino-acids released from H₄ histone have also decreased, resulting in less number of chromophores of Cu-H₄ complex with increasing dose. This can be used as an *in vitro* biological dosimeter (Fig. 4).

The linear increase in H₄ histone depletion with radiation dose from 20 to 70 Gy at 1.12 Gy/s indicates slow depletion of H₄ histone from DNA-H₄ complex. Hydroxyl radicals and hydroperoxy radicals produced by gamma radiation diffuse (diffusion coefficient being $\sim 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)²⁴ near the bonding site. The negatively charged phosphate groups of DNA that were bound with the positively charged amino-acids (e.g. arginine and lysine) slowly get loosened by the attack of these free radicals, finally resulting in cleavage of H₄ histone. Even at 100 Gy, H₄ histone depletion is half of the amount used for complex formation. Hence the complex is moderately strong and offers resistance to radiation dose. DNA-H₄ complex can be used as *in vitro* biological dosimeter from 20 to 70 Gy at a dose rate of 1.12 Gy/s (Table 5).

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